

Medicinal Ecology: Hosts, Parasites, and Antiparasitic as Interacting Ecological Agents

Mostafa A. Elfawal

Program in Molecular Medicine, UMass Chan Medical School, Worcester, MA, USA
Mostafa.Elfawal@umassmed.edu, mostafafawal@gmail.com

Graphical Abstract:

Abstract:

Modern strategies for drug discovery against parasitic diseases are increasingly reliant on a reductionist mindset, focusing more on identifying a single protein target and associated susceptibility within a single parasite. Although this method was effective at discovering some successful antiparasitic compounds, it often neglects the context of the complex host-parasite ecological system. Shaped by coevolution among hosts, parasites, xenobiotics, and host-resident microbiota, these systems closely interact across interconnected chemical and biological gradients. Here, I propose medicinal ecology as a conceptual framework that views antiparasitic drugs as chemical interventions that shaped by and modify host–parasite–microbiota interactions within biologically constrained niches. In medicinal ecology, potential antiparasitic agents may be identified by exploring defense strategies evolved in similar host–parasite or relevant prey-predator ecological systems. Using parasitic helminths as an example, I contend that effective drug discovery and design, therapeutic success, and failure may be better understood within the ecological context of parasitism, including host physiological, behavioral, and physicochemical limitations, interactions among the host-associated biota, and parasite adaptation under exposure. Medicinal ecology addresses the limitations of current antiparasitic discovery programs, especially their low productivity in deploying new agents combined with reduced deployment times due to the evolution of drug resistance, which reductionist models do not fully account for early in the discovery pipeline. By targeting multifactorial and conserved ecological vulnerabilities in a specific host niche rather than isolated molecular events, medicinal ecology offers testable predictions for improved antiparasitic discovery programs, ecologically guided combination therapy, and better resistance management.

Keywords:

Medicinal ecology; Parasites; antiparasitics; Helminths; Anthelmintics; Host–parasite interactions; Microbiome; Chemical ecology; Chemogenomic; Zoopharmacognosy; Ethnopharmacology; Pharmacology; Polypharmacology; Drug development; One Health

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Introduction:

In modern biomedical and pharmacological research, drug discovery predominantly follows a reductionist approach in which new drugs are designed to modulate specific molecular targets in line with Paul Ehrlich's "magic bullet" concept (1). Although it has yielded significant advances in the control of infectious diseases, it often underrepresents the host niche and ecological constraints early in antiparasitic drug discovery.

Here, I introduce the concept of medicinal ecology, which frames antiparasitic agents as ecological forces acting within the dynamic physiological and physicochemical host niche. In this view, antiparasitic drugs do not act in isolation but are mediated by hosts, parasites, and associated microbiota, and actively reshape the interactions among them. The framework integrates knowledge from physiology, immunology, pharmacology, polypharmacology, pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics, microbiome, parasitology, ethnopharmacology, zoology and zoopharmacognosy. Medicinal ecology neither replaces target-based pharmacology nor claims a complete advantage over reductionist drug-discovery strategies; rather, it emphasizes particular ecological contexts—especially host-parasite systems—in which the system's complexity and associated niche constraints significantly influence the outcomes of antiparasitic interventions.

In this discussion, I will use parasitic helminths and vertebrate hosts as host-parasite system models, representing one of the most sophisticated forms of parasitism involving two multilayered metazoan organisms. Besides helminth parasitism, the understanding of medicinal ecology could also extend to other pathogens and host systems. I will use the terms "anthelmintics and antiparasitic" to refer to small-molecule chemotherapies or large-molecule biologics targeting parasitic infections; however, the principle also applies to other antimicrobial agents.

Ecological defense strategies, zoopharmacognosy and ethnopharmacology:

In multiple host-parasite systems spanning all kingdoms of life—including bacteria, Archaea, Protista, Fungi, Plantae, and Animalia—various species have converged on conserved mechanisms for the detection of invading

parasites and activation of antiparasitic chemical defenses. These mechanisms often target biological functions essential for parasite establishment, metabolism, and reproduction. These mechanisms may be adopted as an intervention strategy against parasitism in other host-parasite systems. Nematodes are among the most abundant organisms on Earth and play critical ecological roles in terrestrial, freshwater, and marine ecosystems. In this section, I will use ecological and coevolutionary examples from Nematoda; analogous examples are also present in Platyhelminthes. The examples discussed below should not be considered equally validated; some offer evidence of direct antiparasitic efficacy, others demonstrate ecological defense strategies, and others propose mechanistic hypotheses that warrant further investigation.

In terrestrial soil, direct interactions between bacteria and bacterivorous nematodes are well documented, and soil microorganisms have evolved effective control strategies, including the deployment of chemical secondary metabolites and biological protein toxins, in response to the arms race with soil nematodes. Ivermectin, a powerful broad-spectrum anthelmintic, was isolated from the soil-dwelling bacterium *Streptomyces avermitilis* (2, 3). Cry5B pore-forming crystal proteins, isolated from the soil bacterium *Bacillus thuringiensis* (4, 5). Similarly, soil nematophagous fungi such as *Pochonia chlamydosporia* deploy VCP1, a protease-like enzyme that degrades nematode cuticle and eggshell, thereby compromising nematode viability, fitness, and community growth (6).

Antagonistic interactions between soil nematodes and multiple protist species have been documented; however, these interactions are far more complex than depicted in current soil-food webs. For example, exoproducts isolated from soil amoebae repel nematodes and exhibit nematostatic activity via protein toxins (7). *Cryptodiffugia operculate*, a soil amoeba, employs a highly specialized and species-specific back-hunting prey strategy, fixing and immobilizing, and digesting much larger juveniles and adult stages of soil nematode, likely involving chemical signaling (8). Similarly, *Colpoda steinii*, a soil ciliate, inhibits the feeding, development, and reproduction of the soil nematode (9). *Cercomonas sp.*, a soil flagellate,

was able to attack, bind the cuticle, and kill soil nematodes (10). While these effects were mainly attributed to ecological interactions, the potential role of chemical signaling or secreted bioactive compounds was not fully investigated, leaving open the possibility that protists also evolved their chemical defenses against soil nematodes. Marine nematodes constitute the majority of nematode species on Earth; despite their ecological importance, only a limited proportion of their diversity has been documented (11), leaving most nematode-ecological networks yet to be explored for chemical signals.

Similarly, metazoan organisms parasitized with nematodes have evolved physical and chemical control mechanisms. Plants are among the most sophisticated natural chemists, having evolved a wide array of secondary metabolites to defend against herbivores, pathogens, and parasites. Medicinal plants produce a variety of structurally distinct compounds that often act through multiple, synergistic mechanisms to interfere with biological processes of their enemies. This impressive chemical diversity enhances their ecological resilience and makes plants a primary source of many vital medicines used in human health, including antiparasitic agents (12-15).

Insects also developed their means and chemicals to fight against parasitic infections. For example, bees and assassin bugs produce venoms with anthelmintic activity (16, 17). Even vertebrates developed antiparasitic secondary metabolites. For example, the secondary metabolites: squalamine and trodusquemine, isolated from the stomach and intestines of the dogfish shark *Squalus acanthias*, exhibited broad-spectrum antibacterial activity (18), as well as demonstrated potent anthelmintic activity against human gastrointestinal nematodes (19), supporting the premise that analogous host-parasite ecological systems, including marine vertebrates, can reveal novel antiparasitic strategies.

Even endophytic and symbiotic microorganisms act as ecological proxies for their hosts, producing bioactive molecules that defend their hosts against pathogens and parasites. Extracts from the endophytic fungi isolated from numerous plant species exhibited anthelmintic activity (20, 21). A compelling example is the discovery of emodepside, a promising

anthelmintic targeting the neuromuscular system (22). Emodepside is a direct derivative of the cyclodepsipeptide PF1022A, isolated from an endophytic fungal strain reported as *Mycelia sterilia*, later linked to *Rosellinia*-related fungi, isolated from the leaves of the ornamental plant *Camellia japonica* (23-25). Similarly, multiple bacterial endophytes of the anthelmintic plant *Veronica antheilmintica* were found to exhibit antimicrobial activity (26). Interestingly, the production of artemisinin, an antimalarial agent, in *Artemisia annua* plants was enhanced by chemical signals from endophytes of *A. annua* (27). Insect symbionts, such as *Drosophila* associates *Spiroplasma*, produce ribosome-inactivating proteins that depurinate parasitic nematode ribosomal RNA, targeting the *Drosophila* host (28). Salicylaldehyde, isolated from the gut of zebrafish and putatively produced by the gut microbe *Pelomonas sp.*, showed inhibitory activity against the nematode parasite *Pseudocapillaria tomentosa* egg hatch both *in vitro* and *in vivo* (29).

These are just a few examples illustrating how host species and their associates use biochemical methods to target a wide range of helminth parasites. A significant benefit of applying the medicinal ecology approach is the leverage of information gained from understanding how host organisms control long-term parasites in similar systems. As a result, chemically mediated control strategies may be predicted and optimized to function effectively within the desired host ecology.

In response to parasitic infections, multiple animal species have developed innate and heritable self-medication behavior, ingesting natural products with medicinal properties, mainly from plants or fungi that have a long history of coevolution with parasitic infections (30, 31). Fruit flies, spiders, lizards, elephants, bears, deer, elk, various carnivorous species, and apes, when sick or infected, display self-medication behaviors (32). In response to parasitic helminths, baboons use *Balanites spp.*, to control schistosomiasis (33). Similarly, chimpanzees were found to use medicinal plants such as *Veronica spp.*, *Aspilia spp.*, *Rubia spp.*, and *Manniophyton spp.* to physically and chemically expel gastrointestinal helminths (30, 34). When infected with gastrointestinal nematodes, sheep and goats shift from grazing on

high-quality forage to selectively grazing low-quality, tannin-rich anthelmintic plants (35, 36). Alaskan Brown bears, as well as snow geese, also swallow whole plant leaves to expel tapeworms physically (33); however, it is not clear whether the selected plants possess antiparasitic activity. Changes in appetite and feeding behavior, associated with shifting from a regular diet to foraging, were also observed in parasite-infected fish (37). The essence of zoopharmacognosy is that humans may discover new medicines by studying animals that have used medicinal plants for millions of years. By researching natural products used for self-medication against various ailments and exploring their medicinal properties, we might identify potential therapeutics to combat human infections (30, 32).

It is believed that traditional medicine and the rich ethnopharmacological knowledge originated from observing animal self-medication (33). For generations, humans have depended on natural products across various ethnic groups. Advances in extraction techniques, analytical methods, and computational strategies have helped bridge traditional ethnopharmacology with modern drug discovery, leading to the identification of numerous promising bioactive compounds (38).

Niche filters against anthelmintic agents across helminth parasites:

In vivo effectiveness of antiparasitic drugs is frequently limited by access to parasitized ecological niches within hosts rather than to molecular targets within parasites alone. Helminth parasites are highly adapted to parasitize specific tissues within their hosts, and may act as ecological filters, possibly to evade host immunity and xenobiotics. Therefore, it is unlikely to predict therapeutic activity in infected hosts using target- or whole-organism-based screening platforms that lack representation of host ecological filters.

Gastrointestinal nematodes are embedded within the host's dynamic luminal ecosystem, which includes regular bowel movements, high concentrations of digestive enzymes, an acidic food bolus, a multitude of microbial communities, thick and sticky mucosal barriers, immune cells, and antibodies, all in a microaerophilic environment. Covered by hydrophobic cuticles (39, 40), impeded in layers

of hydrophilic mucin matrix from the host (41), gastrointestinal nematodes are protected from the digestive enzymes, host immunity, and any xenobiotics. Covered by two armor layers of different polarities, gastrointestinal nematodes' exposure to both hydrophilic and hydrophobic compounds is limited. Thus, oral anthelmintics must exhibit balanced physicochemical and ADME properties to limit host absorption and metabolism, increase gut retention, enhance diffusion through the host mucosa, and penetrate the parasite cuticle (42).

Filarial nematodes inhabit various tissue niches, such as lymphatics, blood vessels, skin, and connective tissues, and effective drugs must be systemically absorbed to reach parasitized tissues at therapeutic concentrations. Lymphatic filariae—*Wuchereria bancrofti*, *Brugia malayi*, and *Brugia timori*—live in the host's lymphatic system (Babu and Nutman, 2012), releasing thousands of microfilariae into the bloodstream. Eyeworms, *Loa loa*, live in the connective tissues of eyelids, the subconjunctival space, and the anterior chamber or intraocular (43). River blindness worm, adult *Onchocerca volvulus*, lives in onchocercosis, highly protective fibrous subcutaneous nodules (44). Each female of *O. volvulus* reproduces thousands of microfilariae daily that migrate to vital organs, including the eyes. These microfilariae eventually die in large numbers, including in the eye, triggering a severe immune response and inflammation that can lead to blindness. Larvicidal anthelmintics are prohibited for use against *O. volvulus* to prevent worsening of disease symptoms. Adult heartworms, *Dirofilaria immitis*, reside within the pulmonary vasculature, where systemic drug access is high. Unlike *O. volvulus*, larvicidal treatment for heartworm is preferred over adulticidal treatment. The latter can cause death of adult parasites, provoke severe inflammatory or embolic reactions, and pose risks to the host's safety (45). In *Trichinella spiralis*, the migrating larvae are the pathogenic stage that randomly disseminates throughout the host musculature, reside in modified host cells, and are covered with protective capsules of host collagen, which efficiently restrict the diffusion of xenobiotics and drugs, creating a significant challenge for drug-based intervention (46). Guinea worms, *Dracunculus medinensis*, reside beneath the skin of the host's lower extremities to facilitate

transmission. Oral anthelmintics are often ineffective against *D. medinensis*, potentially because they have limited access to parasitized tissues (47). Rat lungworms, *Angiostrongylus cantonensis*, migrate through the host body and parasitize the nervous system, are protected from systemic drugs, and larval death can drive severe host pathology (48).

Trematodes, flukes, reside in specialized host tissues that provide significant protection. For example, schistosomes occupy intravascular niches with high systemic drug exposure (49), and liver flukes (*Fasciola* spp.) live in the biliary duct and gallbladder (50). Lung flukes (*Paragonimus* spp.) parasitize the host lung tissues covered with highly protective fibrotic capsules (51). These fluke parasites rely on tough, selectively permeable teguments. They are equipped with efficient efflux pumps that eliminate xenobiotics and drugs, making therapeutic control of flukes very challenging (52-55).

Similarly, cestodes demonstrate niche specificity. For example, *Echinococcus* spp., a group of cyst-forming cestodes, reside in physically isolated compartments, hydatid cysts, covered with a solid adventitial layer (Diaz et al., 2023), granting them strong protection against host immunity, xenobiotics, and drugs.

Together, these examples demonstrate that helminths survive in their hosts by exploiting protected niches, limiting the distribution and exposure to xenobiotics and drugs, and imposing an ecological constraint on systemic medications. These adaptations are shaped by millions of years of coevolution among parasites, host immunity, metabolism, and microbial communities. As well as exposure to xenobiotics or medicinal components from host regular or seasonal diets, self-medication behavior, and traditional medicine. From a medicinal ecology standpoint, active anthelmintics should therefore be viewed not as molecular inhibitors, but as ecological effector directed toward a specific host tissue. This view highlights why *in vitro* potency alone rarely predicts clinical success and underscores the need for ecologically guided delivery strategies that explicitly account for tissue accessibility and host tolerance.

Helminth parasites as chemical ecologists:

Parasitic helminths co-evolved within their hosts under the sustained selective pressure of host immune insults, dietary compounds, and an arsenal of metabolites produced by their hosts, associated microbiota, or from the host diet. To gain protection in such a harsh environment, helminth parasites have layers of physical and chemical shields, such as highly protective cuticle or tegument, small-molecule-metabolizing enzymes, and numerous proteases for detoxifying toxin proteins. Therefore, parasitic helminths are not passive drug targets; they are chemical ecologists engaged in an active arms race with their hosts.

Through tissue specificity within their host, excretory/secretory products and extracellular vesicles (56, 57), parasite secondary metabolites (58), and by masking themselves with host molecules (59), helminth parasites actively manipulate host immunity, microbial communities and mediate the inflammatory responses at feeding sites to promote survival, persistence, and facilitate nutrient acquisition required for their reproduction machinery (60, 61).

Parasitic helminths also directly influence their host microbial communities. For example, *Ascaris suum* produces antimicrobial peptides (ASABF) that directly inhibit microbial growth and alter the composition of its host microbiome (62). Helminth-secreted factors ultimately function as ecological effectors that shape the host niche in favor of parasitism. Interestingly, host organisms seem to have adapted to coexist with helminth parasites, relying on these helminth-released ecological factors to regulate their own immune systems, supporting the hygiene hypothesis of autoimmune diseases (63) and regulating host diabetes (64). Medicinal ecology situates these helminth-derived molecules alongside host defenses and microbiome signaling as competing chemical agents within the same ecological arena.

Limitations of the reductionist approach in antiparasitic discovery:

Anthelmintic-parasite exposure rarely occurs in a vacuum, and to be effective, anthelmintics must survive multiple layers of physical and chemical barriers to reach the targeted parasites in their niches. A common challenge in antiparasitic drug discovery is the discrepancy between *ex vivo*

activity against adult helminth parasites and *in vivo* activity in infected animal models. This discrepancy could be partially explained by the poor physicochemical properties of candidate compounds, which lead to poor ADME (Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, and Excretion) and are thus eliminated before reaching the parasitized tissues (42, 65). In contrast, drug metabolism in host tissues may be crucial for converting the parent drug into therapeutically active metabolites that are potent *in vivo*, as with albendazole sulfoxide (66). Drug candidates that frequently fail *in vivo* due to ADME issues can be further optimized using prodrug strategies to achieve the desired *in vivo* performance. (67).

It is estimated that the human microbiome comprises approximately 10^{13} microbial cells, comparable in scale to the number of total host cells (68). The host microbiome may actively metabolize, sequester, or modify drugs, thus mediating parasite exposure and drug efficacy (69, 70). Another potential fate that anthelmintics face within the infected host is sometimes overlooked in the reductionist approach of drug discovery. Finally, *in vitro*-active compounds may target biological functions in parasites that are only essential under *in vitro* conditions.

Medicinal ecology views anthelmintics not merely as molecular modulators of a specific target within helminth parasites, but as chemical pressures that influence biological interactions across multiple levels—from parasites' intracellular homeostasis to host–parasite–microbiome interconnected networks, considering the ecological impact on the host, parasites, and microbiome communities that co-inhabit the host niche. This perspective is especially important for a broader understanding of parasitic infections. From a medicinal ecology standpoint, anthelmintic treatment is considered an acute disturbance to the ecology of helminth communities within their vertebrate hosts— analogous to sudden starvation, invasive outbreaks, or exposure to severe environmental stressors in other ecological systems.

The desired outcomes of successful anthelmintic treatment include mass death of the helminth community, paralysis, and expulsion from the host's protected niches. At the host level, an optimal anthelmintic should have little or no negative effect on the host's homeostasis and

physiology, and on its associated microbial communities.

In this ecological frame, anthelmintics are analogous to targeted, self-limited biological agents that aim to suppress or displace invasive species within natural ecosystems. Success depends on these agents' ability to survive in the new environment, actively locate the invasive species, and either eliminate or displace them. The effectiveness of such biological control is assessed not only by reducing the invasive population but also by preserving the surrounding ecological community. Medicinal ecology is not meant to replace target-based pharmacology but to expand it by adding ecological and spatial factors that affect therapeutic results.

The art of ecological combination and drug resistance:

For thousands of years, human ailments, specifically parasitic infections, were treated with remedies in their natural forms, mostly medicinal plants, comprising a combination of medicinal chemical components. Although composition and dosing can vary, and results are not universally applicable, several well-studied systems show that defense agents in their natural forms, within the evolutionarily selected combination, can surpass purified forms and may slow the evolution of drug resistance;(71, 72). Employing purified or synthetic compounds in the fight against infectious diseases is a modern concept, developed after the Industrial Revolution in the 19th century (73). This shift may have altered selection pressure on human pathogens and contributed to the evolution of resistance in some infectious diseases.

Plants have adaptive and inducible defense strategies— analogous to generating pathogen-specific antibodies in vertebrates—they produce or release various small toxic molecules to repel or attenuate threats (74), such as viruses, bacteria, fungi, parasites, insects, and herbivorous animals. The annual wormwood, *Artemisia annua*, produces a diverse array of bioactive compounds that offer strong protection against both microscopic and larger threats, such as trematode helminths. It is best known for its antimalarial properties. *A. annua* has been used for thousands of years in traditional medicine to treat malaria-associated intermittent fevers. Isolated from *A. annua*, artemisinin, the potent

antimalarial drug, also exhibits anthelmintic activity against trematode parasites, including schistosomiasis (75). Interestingly, the antimalarial mode of action of artemisinin is not fully understood (76). To protect plant cells from these biologically active metabolites, they are produced and stored in specialized structures, the glandular trichomes, which synthesize, store, and secrete substantial amounts of phytochemicals, including artemisinin, additional terpenoids, and flavonoids (71). Delivery of artemisinin in its natural form, as the dried whole plant of *Artemisia annua* (77) was reported to be more effective against malaria parasites than a comparable dose of pure artemisinin (78) to overcome artemisinin resistance. It was more resilient against the evolution of drug resistance (71). Whole-plant therapy of *A. annua* also demonstrated enhanced pharmacokinetics with a >40-fold increase in the amount of artemisinin that entered the bloodstream compared to pure artemisinin (79). Similarly, cinchona bark, the source of quinine, the early-generation antimalarial compound, was found to have better antimalarial activity than purified quinine and to overcome quinine resistance, potentially due to synergy between at least 30 Cinchona alkaloids (72).

Analogous complex combinations were observed with microbes that produce antiparasitic compounds, analogous to those found in medicinal plants. Ivermectin is a semi-synthetic derivative of the avermectins, macrocyclic lactones produced by *Streptomyces avermitilis*. The genome of *S. avermitilis* contains 30-40 biosynthetic gene clusters, suggesting strong potential to produce a wide range of secondary metabolites, although only some have been experimentally identified (80). In addition to avermectins (e.g., A1a, A2a, B1a, B1b), *S. avermitilis* produces multiple active compounds, including oligomycins (antifungal) and filipins (cytotoxic). Interestingly, oligomycin A was independently reported to have broad-spectrum anthelmintic activity against gastrointestinal nematodes (19). Besides the eight anthelmintic cyclodepsipeptides (PF1022 A-H), produced by *Rosellinia sp.* fungi, multiple antimicrobial cytochalasins and antimicrobial proteins are also produced (81, 82). Cytochalasins carry antiparasitic activity against *Trypanosoma cruzi* and *Leishmania infantum* (83).

The anthelmintic crystal (Cry) proteins, such as Cry5B, produced by *B. thuringiensis*, are pore-forming δ -endotoxins with potent activity against nematodes, including parasitic gastrointestinal helminths, through binding to specific glycolipid receptors in the worm intestine and disrupting epithelial integrity (4, 5, 84-86). Inactivated whole bacterial cells containing Cry5B crystals demonstrated better *in vivo* efficacy than purified Cry5B protein alone, likely due to protection from proteolytic degradation in the gastrointestinal tract (87, 88). Another plausible scenario is that synergism among natural bioactive factors produced by *B. thuringiensis*—including non-Cry virulence factors such as metalloproteases, chitinases, thuringiensin, and zwittermycin A contributes to the observed activity (89-91). Interestingly, thuringiensin and zwittermycin A, were found to enhance the insecticidal effects of Cry proteins (89, 92, 93). Thus, these synergies could similarly enhance the anthelmintic activity of *B. thuringiensis* whole-bacterial formulations relative to purified Cry alone. Interestingly, the crystal structure of *B. thuringiensis* crystal proteins identified multiple small-molecule binding sites predicted, supporting the potential role of Cry proteins' small-molecule interactions. Using yeast cells as an example, the total theoretically estimated interactions between proteins and various molecules are estimated to be ~20% for protein-small molecule interactions, the second most after protein-protein (67%), and more than protein-DNA (5.4%) and protein-RNA (6.4%) interactions (94). However, in research, protein-small molecule interactions still lag behind the other types.

Across host kingdoms, the activities of medicinal plants' defensive secondary metabolites against the pathogens of mammalian hosts seem coincidental at first. However, there is a plausible evolutionary reason for this cross-kingdom protection. For example, in the case of *Artemisia annua* and its activity against malaria parasites. Malaria parasites harbor apicoplasts, derived from the same ancestral cyanobacterial endosymbiont that also gave rise to plant chloroplasts (95). The presence of chloroplast-like organelles of cyanobacterial origin and pathways in malaria parasites explains the biological activity of *A. annua*, which possesses a repertoire of antibacterial and allelopathic

(inhibiting competing plants) secondary metabolites against apicomplexan parasites, including malaria parasites (71). Interestingly, artemisinin harbors potent allelopathic activity (96), and several plant-derived allelopathic compounds (herbicidal) have been shown to specifically kill apicomplexan parasites such as *P. falciparum*, *Cryptosporidium parvum*, and *Toxoplasma gondii* (97).

Among the many essential phytochemicals produced by medicinal plants are terpenoids, the main components of essential oils, which give most medicinal plants a distinctive fragrance. Terpenoids are made up of 5-carbon isoprene units and/or their dimethylallyl isomers, which can include extensive branching and cyclization. The ability of plants to generate a nearly unlimited variety of terpenoids through elongation, cyclization, and secondary chemical transformations enhances their parasite-killing activity against multiple parasite species (71, 98, 99). In addition, medicinal plants contain a wide range of flavonoids, tannins, lignans, coumarins, saponins, quinones, and lectins, as well as antimicrobial peptides. The whole plant form of medicinal plants may exhibit greater antiparasitic activity due to synergistic interactions among these metabolites (71, 72, 100). Improvement in whole-plant forms over their pure constituents may be explained by enhanced bioavailability of their key bioactive agents, driven by the inhibition of hepatic and intestinal cytochrome P450 enzymes that metabolize xenobiotics and drugs (71, 79).

Additionally, some phytochemicals from medicinal plants are known immunomodulators that stimulate host defenses against invading parasites; others reduce toxicity or side effects; and others direct key phytochemicals to the targeted site in the body, thereby improving overall therapeutic performance. Medicinal plants also produce secondary metabolites that modulate host pharmacokinetics by inhibiting metabolic enzymes, thereby improving the bioavailability of active compounds (71, 79). Through this evolutionary multi-target and combination strategy, plants can maintain effectiveness against numerous species of evolving parasites—a paradigm fundamentally different from single-compound pharmacology.

The principle of “monarch, minister, assistant, and guide” in traditional Chinese

medicine is among the most advanced historical prescriptions for rational combination therapy (101, 102). In this combination, the monarch herb provides compounds that drive the primary therapeutic effects against the treated indication, while the minister herb shares pharmacological components that enhance overall therapeutic effectiveness. The assistant optimizes the combination, either boosting synergy, reducing toxicity, or balancing side effects, while the guide targets specific organs or tissues (101, 103, 104). Rather than depending on a single active ingredient, this framework facilitates coordinated, multi-target interventions across biological pathways, combining pharmacodynamic synergy with pharmacokinetic regulation. From medicinal ecology, it demonstrates how complex mixtures can serve as adaptive, systemic therapies that engage host, pathogen, and physiological factors concurrently. It offers a conceptual plan for designing modern combination therapy that is both effective against parasites in their host niche and promotes safety in treated hosts, and is resilient to the evolution of drug resistance.

From a medicinal ecology perspective, drug resistance is not solely due to mutations at specific drug targets but also as an ecological response to ongoing chemical pressures. Drug resistance reflects how parasites adapt to the ecological agent, including host pharmacokinetics, tissue environments, stress responses, and interactions with the host microbiota. This ecological view may better explain multidrug anthelmintic resistance, which cannot be fully accounted for by classical target-based mechanisms alone. For example, *Haemonchus contortus* and *Ancylostoma caninum* developed resistance to multiple anthelmintic classes, including combination therapies, through mechanisms that extend beyond mutations on the targeted molecules (105-109). A parallel example is seen in *P. falciparum* resistance to artemisinin-based therapies. Artemisinin resistance is not primarily driven by a loss of drug–target interaction, but by parasite quiescence and stress adaptations that enable transient survival during periods of peak drug exposure (110-112).

Over millions of years in the fight against their foes, plants rely on complex mixtures of secondary metabolites that act together through

complementary, often synergistic mechanisms, putting selection pressures to evolve resistance. In response, plants have evolved multiple integrated chemical defenses that target the resistance mechanisms developed by their parasites (113). Instead of targeting single pathway plants evolve combinations that act on multiple biological targets, thereby enhancing overall efficacy. This makes it harder for plant parasites to acquire additional resistance-associated mutations, which often carry a fitness cost.

Phytochemicals that target parasite resistance mechanisms, including terpenes, flavonoids, alkaloids, and polyphenols, which interfere with multidrug resistance systems, including efflux pumps, and can restore sensitivity to active agents (72). For example, terpenes have been proposed to inhibit efflux pumps associated with multidrug resistance (114, 115), potentially through interactions influenced by their structural diversity.

The magic bullets concept against parasitic organisms led to the repeated use of single purified therapies, which were naturally selected for resistant micro- and macroorganisms. The advantages seen in the first half of the 20th century in medicine and agriculture were reversed in the second half by the rise of resistance to antibiotics, antiparasitic, insecticides, and herbicides (71). A renewed appreciation for evolution and the adaptive potential of the targeted organisms has led to more sustainable approaches that combine control agents in combination therapies. The success of the combinatorial approach is evident throughout nature, as exemplified by medicinal plants that harbor repertoires of hundreds of compounds that comprise their defense systems. This strategy exploits the pharmacokinetic dynamics of treatment and represents an ecological adaptation to pulsed chemical pressure, not solely by a classical mutation in the target protein. Indeed, if plants had followed the pharmaceutical model of serial production of single-component protection against their enemies, they might have faced strong evolutionary constraints (72).

In ecological terms, drug resistance is a rewiring of multiple factors acting as niche filters, including enhanced efflux capacity, changes in feeding behavior or reproductive strategies, altered parasite metabolism, or enter metabolic

quiescence when exposed to high concentrations of xenobiotics. These adaptations are influenced by the dynamics of xenobiotic or drug exposure, which shape parasite physiology and behavior. Recognizing resistance as an ecological phenomenon suggests that more effective therapeutic strategies may involve designed combination interventions that simultaneously target multiple ecological responses—such as stress tolerance, nutrient acquisition, secretion, and niche occupancy—thereby reducing the opportunity for evolutionary escape.

Modern tools and medicinal ecology recommendations:

Phenotypic screens of *ex vivo* parasites are essential tools for discovering anthelmintics. Instead of only asking which compounds kill these parasites, we can also investigate which compounds reveal biological vulnerabilities across life stages or ecological contexts, such as in vertebrate hosts or vector organisms. Therefore, phenotypic screens can provide a more comprehensive ecological understanding that could help in designing effective intervention strategies. Chemical libraries could serve as ecological probes, systematically examining how parasites respond to disruptions in signaling, metabolism, detoxification, and structural integrity, which are essential to successful parasitism.

When viewed in this light, patterns that emerge across independent screens are as informative as individual hits and could reveal weaknesses in parasites shaped by host-parasite coevolution. Across independent phenotypic screens, a consistent ecological signal emerges. Compounds with robust activity against adult parasitic nematodes could reveal chemical strategies that evolved through hostile biological interactions with helminth parasites. In our earlier FDA-approved drug screen (2019), adult hookworm actives already included semi-synthetic natural product derivatives (ivermectin, selamectin), microbial ionophores (monensin, salinomycin), and plant alkaloids (nicotine, physostigmine), as well as cationic dyes and surfactants with alkaloid-like properties (116). These same ecological chemotypes re-emerged in our large-scale screen of more than 30,000 compounds, which was expanded to include additional microbial natural products

(oligomycin A, bafilomycin A1, staurosporine), fungal-derived derivatives (emodepside), plant defensive metabolites (dioscin), and vertebrate host-defense aminosterols (squalamine, trodusquemine) (19). Despite their diverse origins, these compounds converge on a narrow set of conserved biological constraints, most importantly the neuromuscular signaling, membrane integrity, ion and redox homeostasis, mitochondrial energy metabolism, and nutrient-sensing pathways, that remain essential for parasites survival across host environments.

Significantly, this ecological pattern extends beyond traditional natural products; many effective compounds are synthetic molecules that mimic natural products, replicating the ecological constraints on helminth parasites. These include cationic dyes and surfactants (e.g., crystal violet, dithiazanine, cetylpyridinium) that mimic alkaloid-like membrane disruptors, phenolic and flavonoid-inspired kinase inhibitors that echo plant allelochemicals, and redox-active or metal-chelating compounds that mimic microbial toxins. From a medicinal ecology perspective, these findings suggest that pharmaceuticals are most effective when they operate as ecological agents within host–parasite chemical networks rather than as narrowly optimized, single-target inhibitors.

Medicinal ecology should not be confused with traditional medicine, even though it takes inspiration from natural systems and ethnopharmacology. Instead, it is a forward-looking, experimentally derived approach that uses advanced tools to study and explore host–parasite systems. Drug discovery, viewed through this lens, may represent systematic identification and optimization of chemical strategies that evolution has already validated as practical means of interfering with parasitic survival in analogous host–parasite ecosystems. Medicinal ecology leverages advances in modern research tools, such as high-throughput screening and systems biology approaches, including chemical genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, metabolomics, lipidomics, and metagenomics, to understand how interactions among genes, proteins, metabolites, cells, and environments give rise to complex phenotypes—such as parasite survival, host response, or drug efficacy, aiming to identify ecological vulnerabilities and

useful multitarget compounds that modulate parasitism in favor of the host species. By combining modern screening techniques and systems biology tools with ecological concepts, medicinal ecology advances beyond the limits of reductionist pharmacology and traditional remedies, providing a logical, scalable approach to developing better, ecologically informed antiparasitic treatments.

Viewing parasitic infection through a medicinal ecology lens encourages the development of discovery pipelines that move beyond single-species, survival-based screens toward ecologically informed assays that capture how parasites persist within host environments. One immediate goal is to integrate screening across multiple helminth species to identify conserved parasitism-associated ecological vulnerabilities, rather than relying solely on species-specific molecular targets. Such comparative approaches are more likely to reveal shared physiological constraints shaped by host ecology and evolutionary pressure.

Medicinal ecology further recommends experimental designs that, in addition to measuring parasite survival, also assess ecological factors affecting parasite persistence and transmission, such as motility, attachment, feeding, secretion, fecundity, and stress in parasitized host tissues.

By applying medicinal ecology, studying multiple analogous host–parasite systems, we may better predict potential antiparasitic agents that induce ecological constraints and disrupt stress responses, nutrient sensing, movement, or secretion, thereby exhibiting broader anthelmintic efficacy. Direct test in infected hosts, or under host-like conditions—with the integration of host tissues, cells, lymph, blood, bile, and the microbiome, and host environmental conditions (temperature, pH, and oxygen gradients), may enable the discovery of more effective and more progressive antiparasitic agents. Ecologically guided combination therapies, in the context of multi-axis ecological pressures, may slow or help prevent the evolution of drug resistance, thereby limiting the space for evolutionary escape.

Because therapeutic outcomes are influenced by host context, adopting screening platforms that incorporate host tissues, parasites,

and the microbiome when feasible may be particularly informative. Incorporating helminth parasites into new emerging systems—such as gut-on-chip (117), tissue-on-chip platforms (118), or organoid-based platforms (119) that recreate flow, mucus barriers, oxygen, and pH gradients, and microbial metabolism—offer promising avenues for recreating or mimicking the ecological landscapes encountered within the host niche.

Finally, medicinal ecology encourages the use of screening strategies that reflect the spatial and chemical heterogeneity of parasitized host tissues. By prioritizing compounds active across relevant physiological conditions, we may better predict *in vivo* efficacy and constrain the ecological pathways for resistance evolution. Together, these strategies position medicinal ecology not only as a conceptual framework but as a practical guide for designing more predictive discovery programs.

The concept of medicinal ecology could generate multiple testable predictions, including: (i) leads selected based on activity against parasitic organisms will outperform those active only against free-living screening models; (ii) leads active across multiple screening conditions that mimic the host niche will better predict *in vivo* efficacy than those optimized under a single condition; (iii) leads targeting ecologically essential functions, such as the neuromuscular system, nutrient sensing, host-parasite signaling, and stress responses, will yield broader-spectrum anthelmintics; (iv) multitarget, parasite-specific leads will outperform single-target leads in activity and resilience against drug resistance; (v) combination therapies targeting complementary ecological functions, such as cuticle integrity, metabolism, and the neuromuscular system, will outperform any single component and reduce the rate of resistance emergence; and (vi) compounds with optimized physicochemical properties for better AMDE and targeted host niches will outperform those optimized solely for target affinity.

Medicinal ecology and One Health:

Medicinal ecology aligns naturally with a One Health perspective. Parasites infect a wide range of host organisms, including humans, livestock, wildlife, and plants, often sharing conserved physiological strategies across hosts and

environments. Chemical pressures used against parasites or relevant organisms from soil and marine microorganisms, plants, insects, and animals overlap more than traditionally appreciated. By integrating ecological chemistry with pharmacology, medicinal ecology provides a framework for identifying shared parasite vulnerabilities across multiple parasitic systems, enabling cross-fertilization between human medicine, veterinary science, and agriculture. Screening natural products from plants, fungi, and soil microbes—organisms that have long coexisted with human parasites—becomes not just a discovery strategy, but an ecological inquiry into how chemical warfare has shaped parasite evolution.

Why a new term matters:

While systems pharmacology focuses on multi-omics and pharmacokinetics, medicinal ecology specifically centers on the host-parasite ecological niche as its primary unit of analysis. It highlights the importance of spatial constraints, chemical warfare, community interactions, and evolutionary pressures in shaping resistance and affecting therapeutic outcomes. By integrating host-parasite signaling pathways, microbiome analyses, pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic studies in parasitized animal models, and understanding genetic polymorphisms in both host and parasite populations, we can develop predictive ecological models for therapeutic effectiveness.

The term *medicinal ecology* is not intended to replace pharmacology, chemical biology, or disease ecology, but to bridge them conceptually. Naming the framework enforces that therapeutics are ecological events with evolutionary consequences, and understanding these interacting dynamics can identify novel therapeutics with improved durability, selectivity, and translational success.

Author's note:

The medicinal ecology concept proposed here is intended to stimulate discussion to generate bridges across multiple disciplines, rather than being taken as a rigid theoretical model. In an era of growing drug resistance and limited therapeutics, medicinal ecology addresses an old challenge with new clarity: effective medicines are not just target inhibitors, but ecological forces

shaping host-parasite interactions. Understanding how they act within living systems may be as important as knowing what they bind.

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References:

1. Strebhardt K, Ullrich A. Paul Ehrlich's magic bullet concept: 100 years of progress. *Nat Rev Cancer*. 2008;8(6):473–80.
2. Crump A, Omura S. Ivermectin, 'wonder drug' from Japan: the human use perspective. *Proc Jpn Acad Ser B Phys Biol Sci*. 2011;87(2):13–28.
3. Omura S, Ikeda H, Ishikawa J, Hanamoto A, Takahashi C, Shinose M, et al. Genome sequence of an industrial microorganism *Streptomyces avermitilis*: deducing the ability of producing secondary metabolites. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2001;98(21):12215–20.
4. Hu Y, Georghiou SB, Kelleher AJ, Aroian RV. *Bacillus thuringiensis* Cry5B protein is highly efficacious as a single-dose therapy against an intestinal roundworm infection in mice. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*. 2010;4(3):e614.
5. Hu Y, Miller M, Zhang B, Nguyen TT, Nielsen MK, Aroian RV. In vivo and in vitro studies of Cry5B and nicotinic acetylcholine receptor agonist anthelmintics reveal a powerful and unique combination therapy against intestinal nematode parasites. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*. 2018;12(5):e0006506.
6. Ward E, Kerry BR, Manzanilla-Lopez RH, Mutua G, Devonshire J, Kimenju J, et al. The *Pochonia chlamydosporia* serine protease gene *vcp1* is subject to regulation by carbon, nitrogen and pH: implications for nematode biocontrol. *PLoS One*. 2012;7(4):e35657.
7. Neidig N, Jousset A, Nunes F, Bonkowski M, Paul RJ, Scheu S. Interference between bacterial feeding nematodes and amoebae relies on innate and inducible mutual toxicity. *Functional Ecology*. 2010;24(5):1133–8.
8. Geisen S, Rosengarten J, Koller R, Mulder C, Urich T, Bonkowski M. Pack hunting by a common soil amoeba on nematodes. *Environ Microbiol*. 2015;17(11):4538–46.
9. Griffiths BS. Mineralization of nitrogen and phosphorus by mixed cultures of the ciliate protozoan *Colpoda steinii*, the nematode *Rhabditis* SP. and the bacterium *Pseudomonas fluorescens*. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*. 1986;18(6):637–41.
10. Bjørnlund L, Rønn R. 'David and Goliath' of the soil food web – Flagellates that kill nematodes. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*. 2008;40(8):2032–9.
11. Dache E, Zeppilli D, Sarrazin J, Singh R, Baldrighi E, Miljutin D, et al. MarNemaFunDiv: a first comprehensive dataset of functional traits for marine nematodes. *Sci Data*. 2025;12(1):752.
12. Romero-Benavides JC, Ruano AL, Silva-Rivas R, Castillo-Veintimilla P, Vivanco-Jaramillo S, Bailon-Moscoso N. Medicinal plants used as anthelmintics: Ethnomedical, pharmacological, and phytochemical studies. *Eur J Med Chem*. 2017;129:209–17.
13. Ahmed H, Kilinc SG, Celik F, Kesik HK, Simsek S, Ahmad KS, et al. An Inventory of Anthelmintic Plants across the Globe. *Pathogens*. 2023;12(1).
14. Wink M. Medicinal plants: a source of anti-parasitic secondary metabolites. *Molecules*. 2012;17(11):12771–91.
15. Desmedt W, Mangelinckx S, Kyndt T, Vanholme B. A Phytochemical Perspective on Plant Defense Against Nematodes. *Front Plant Sci*. 2020;11:602079.
16. Fischer-Carvalho A, Taveira-Barbosa TC, Verjovski-Almeida S, Haerberlein S, Sena Amaral M. Antischistosomal Potential of Animal-Derived Natural Products and Compounds. *Microorganisms*. 2025;13(2).
17. Tonk M, Vilcinskis A, Grevelding CG, Haerberlein S. Anthelmintic Activity of Assassin Bug Venom against the Blood Fluke *Schistosoma mansoni*. *Antibiotics (Basel)*. 2020;9(10).
18. Kazakova O, Giniyatullina G, Babkov D, Wimmer Z. From Marine Metabolites to the Drugs of the Future: Squalamine, Trodusquemine, Their Steroid and Triterpene Analogues. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2022;23(3).
19. Elfawal MA, Goetz E, Kim Y, Chen P, Savinov SN, Barasa L, et al. High-Throughput Screening of More Than 30,000 Compounds for Anthelmintics against Gastrointestinal Nematode Parasites. *ACS Infect Dis*. 2024.

20. Farhat H, Urooj F, Sohail N, Ansari M, Ehteshamul-Haque S. Evaluation of nematicidal potential of endophytic fungi associated with healthy plants and GC-MS profiling of metabolites of endophytic *Fusarium solani*. *South African Journal of Botany*. 2022;146:146–61.
21. Praveen K, Mable V, Maria Grace J, Asha R, Leyon V. Identification and bioactivities of endophytic fungi from *Lagenandra toxicaria* Dalz. and *Kaempferia rotunda* L. *Journal of Applied Biology & Biotechnology*. 2020.
22. Saeger B, Schmitt-Wrede HP, Dehnhardt M, Benten WP, Krucken J, Harder A, et al. Latrophilin-like receptor from the parasitic nematode *Haemonchus contortus* as target for the anthelmintic depsipeptide PF1022A. *FASEB J*. 2001;15(7):1332–4.
23. Sasaki T, Takagi M, Yaguchi T, Miyadoh S, Okada T, Koyama M. A new anthelmintic cyclodepsipeptide, PF1022A. *J Antibiot (Tokyo)*. 1992;45(5):692–7.
24. Jeschke R, Iinuma K, Harder A, Schindler M, Murakami T. Influence of the cyclooctadepsipeptides PF1022A and PF1022E as natural products on the design of semi-synthetic anthelmintics such as emodepside. *Parasitology Research*. 2005;97(1):S11–S6.
25. Wittstein K, Cordsmeier A, Lambert C, Wendt L, Sir EB, Weber J, et al. Identification of *Rosellinia* species as producers of cyclodepsipeptide PF1022 A and resurrection of the genus *Dematophora* as inferred from polythetic taxonomy. *Stud Mycol*. 2020;96:1–16.
26. Rustamova N, Wubulikasimu A, Mukhamedov N, Gao Y, Egamberdieva D, Yili A. Endophytic Bacteria Associated with Medicinal Plant *Vernonia anthelmintica*: Diversity and Characterization. *Curr Microbiol*. 2020;77(8):1457–65.
27. Li J, Zhao GZ, Varma A, Qin S, Xiong Z, Huang HY, et al. An endophytic *Pseudonocardia* species induces the production of artemisinin in *Artemisia annua*. *PLoS One*. 2012;7(12):e51410.
28. Hamilton PT, Peng F, Boulanger MJ, Perlman SJ. A ribosome-inactivating protein in a *Drosophila* defensive symbiont. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2016;113(2):350–5.
29. Hammer AJ, Gaulke CA, Garcia-Jaramillo M, Leong C, Morre J, Sieler MJ, Jr., et al. Gut microbiota metabolically mediate intestinal helminth infection in zebrafish. *mSystems*. 2024;9(9):e0054524.
30. de Roode JC, Lefevre T, Hunter MD. Ecology. Self-medication in animals. *Science*. 2013;340(6129):150–1.
31. Hardy K. Paleomedicine and the Evolutionary Context of Medicinal Plant Use. *Rev Bras Farmacogn*. 2021;31(1):1–15.
32. Shurkin J. News feature: Animals that self-medicate. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2014;111(49):17339–41.
33. Huffman MA. Animal self-medication and ethno-medicine: exploration and exploitation of the medicinal properties of plants. *Proc Nutr Soc*. 2003;62(2):371–81.
34. McLennan MR, Hasegawa H, Bardi M, Huffman MA. Gastrointestinal parasite infections and self-medication in wild chimpanzees surviving in degraded forest fragments within an agricultural landscape mosaic in Uganda. *PLoS One*. 2017;12(7):e0180431.
35. Lisonbee LD, Villalba JJ, Provenza FD, Hall JO. Tannins and self-medication: Implications for sustainable parasite control in herbivores. *Behav Processes*. 2009;82(2):184–9.
36. Villalba JJ, Miller J, Ungar ED, Landau SY, Glendinning J. Ruminant self-medication against gastrointestinal nematodes: evidence, mechanism, and origins. *Parasite*. 2014;21:31.
37. Barber I, Hoare D, Krause J. Effects of parasites on fish behaviour: a review and evolutionary perspective. *Reviews in Fish Biology and Fisheries*. 2000;10(2):131–65.
38. Pirintsos S, Panagiotopoulos A, Bariotakis M, Daskalakis V, Lionis C, Sourvinos G, et al. From Traditional Ethnopharmacology to Modern Natural Drug Discovery: A Methodology Discussion and Specific Examples. *Molecules*. 2022;27(13).

39. Fetterer RH, Rhoads ML. Biochemistry of the nematode cuticle: relevance to parasitic nematodes of livestock. *Vet Parasitol.* 1993;46(1-4):103–11.
40. Wright KA. The nematode's cuticle--its surface and the epidermis: function, homology, analogy--a current consensus. *J Parasitol.* 1987;73(6):1077–83.
41. Linden SK, Sutton P, Karlsson NG, Korolik V, McGuckin MA. Mucins in the mucosal barrier to infection. *Mucosal Immunol.* 2008;1(3):183–97.
42. Elfawal MA, Banas V, Rosa BA, Mahoney M, Goetz E, Chen P, et al. Anthelmintics Derived from the Kinase Inhibitor SGI-1776 for the Treatment of Gastrointestinal Worm Infections. *ACS Infect Dis.* 2025.
43. Hassan S, Isyaku M, Yayo A, Sarkin Fada F, Ihesiolor GU, Iliyasu G. Adult Loa loa Filarial Worm in the Anterior Chamber of the Eye: A First Report from Savanna Belt of Northern Nigeria. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis.* 2016;10(4):e0004436.
44. Richards F, Jr., Rizzo N, Diaz Espinoza CE, Monroy ZM, Crovella Valdez CG, de Cabrera RM, et al. One Hundred Years After Its Discovery in Guatemala by Rodolfo Robles, *Onchocerca volvulus* Transmission Has Been Eliminated from the Central Endemic Zone. *Am J Trop Med Hyg.* 2015;93(6):1295–304.
45. Bowman DD, Atkins CE. Heartworm biology, treatment, and control. *Vet Clin North Am Small Anim Pract.* 2009;39(6):1127–58, vii.
46. Sun XM, Hao CY, Wu AQ, Luo ZN, El-Ashram S, Alouffi A, et al. *Trichinella spiralis* - induced immunomodulation signatures on gut microbiota and metabolic pathways in mice. *PLoS Pathog.* 2024;20(1):e1011893.
47. Simonetti O, Zerbato V, Maurel C, Cosimi L, Babich S, Cavalli F, et al. The current state of knowledge on dracunculiasis: a narrative review of a rare neglected disease. *Infez Med.* 2023;31(4):500–8.
48. Barratt J, Chan D, Sandaradura I, Malik R, Spielman D, Lee R, et al. *Angiostrongylus cantonensis*: a review of its distribution, molecular biology and clinical significance as a human pathogen. *Parasitology.* 2016;143(9):1087–118.
49. McManus DP, Dunne DW, Sacko M, Utzinger J, Vennervald BJ, Zhou XN. Schistosomiasis. *Nat Rev Dis Primers.* 2018;4(1):13.
50. Lalor R, Cwiklinski K, Calvani NED, Dorey A, Hamon S, Corrales JL, et al. Pathogenicity and virulence of the liver flukes *Fasciola hepatica* and *Fasciola Gigantica* that cause the zoonosis Fasciolosis. *Virulence.* 2021;12(1):2839–67.
51. Blair D. Lung flukes of the genus *Paragonimus*: ancient and re-emerging pathogens. *Parasitology.* 2022;149(10):1286–95.
52. Cornford EM. *Schistosoma mansoni*, *S. japonicum*, and *S. haematobium*: permeability to acidic amino acids and effect of separated and unseparated adults. *Exp Parasitol.* 1985;59(3):355–63.
53. Wilson RA, Jones MK. Fifty years of the schistosome tegument: discoveries, controversies, and outstanding questions. *Int J Parasitol.* 2021;51(13-14):1213–32.
54. Ravida A, Cwiklinski K, Aldridge AM, Clarke P, Thompson R, Gerlach JQ, et al. *Fasciola hepatica* Surface Tegument: Glycoproteins at the Interface of Parasite and Host. *Mol Cell Proteomics.* 2016;15(10):3139–53.
55. Greenberg RM. Schistosome ABC multidrug transporters: From pharmacology to physiology. *Int J Parasitol Drugs Drug Resist.* 2014;4(3):301–9.
56. Ferreira I, Smyth D, Gaze S, Aziz A, Giacomini P, Ruysers N, et al. Hookworm excretory/secretory products induce interleukin-4 (IL-4)+ IL-10+ CD4+ T cell responses and suppress pathology in a mouse model of colitis. *Infect Immun.* 2013;81(6):2104–11.
57. Wong Y, Rosa BA, Becker L, Camberis M, LeGros G, Zhan B, et al. Proteomic characterization and comparison of the infective and adult life stage secretomes from *Necator americanus* and *Ancylostoma*

- ceylanicum. PLoS Negl Trop Dis. 2025;19(1):e0012780.
58. Wangchuk P, Shepherd C, Constantinoiu C, Ryan RYM, Kouremenos KA, Becker L, et al. Hookworm-Derived Metabolites Suppress Pathology in a Mouse Model of Colitis and Inhibit Secretion of Key Inflammatory Cytokines in Primary Human Leukocytes. *Infect Immun*. 2019;87(4).
59. Dagenais M, Tritten L. Hidden in plain sight: How helminths manage to thrive in host blood. *Front Parasitol*. 2023;2:1128299.
60. Maizels RM, McSorley HJ. Regulation of the host immune system by helminth parasites. *J Allergy Clin Immunol*. 2016;138(3):666–75.
61. Llinas-Caballero K, Caraballo L. Helminths and Bacterial Microbiota: The Interactions of Two of Humans' "Old Friends". *Int J Mol Sci*. 2022;23(21).
62. Kato Y, Komatsu S. ASABF, a novel cysteine-rich antibacterial peptide isolated from the nematode *Ascaris suum*. Purification, primary structure, and molecular cloning of cDNA. *J Biol Chem*. 1996;271(48):30493–8.
63. Smallwood TB, Giacomini PR, Loukas A, Mulvenna JP, Clark RJ, Miles JJ. Helminth Immunomodulation in Autoimmune Disease. *Front Immunol*. 2017;8:453.
64. Berbudi A, Ajendra J, Wardani AP, Hoerauf A, Hubner MP. Parasitic helminths and their beneficial impact on type 1 and type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Metab Res Rev*. 2016;32(3):238–50.
65. Banas V, Elfawal MA, Rosa BA, Mahoney M, Kauffman J, Goetz E, et al. Discovery of Human PIM Kinase Inhibitors as a Class of Anthelmintic Drugs to Treat Intestinal Nematode Infections. *ACS Infect Dis*. 2025.
66. Dayan AD. Albendazole, mebendazole and praziquantel. Review of non-clinical toxicity and pharmacokinetics. *Acta Trop*. 2003;86(2-3):141–59.
67. Brown DG, Park H. Current and Emerging Prodrug Strategies. *J Med Chem*. 2025;68(12):12369–91.
68. Ursell LK, Metcalf JL, Parfrey LW, Knight R. Defining the human microbiome. *Nutr Rev*. 2012;70 Suppl 1(Suppl 1):S38–44.
69. Verdegaal AA, Goodman AL. Integrating the gut microbiome and pharmacology. *Sci Transl Med*. 2024;16(732):eadg8357.
70. Zimmermann M, Zimmermann-Kogadeeva M, Wegmann R, Goodman AL. Mapping human microbiome drug metabolism by gut bacteria and their genes. *Nature*. 2019;570(7762):462–7.
71. Elfawal MA, Towler MJ, Reich NG, Weathers PJ, Rich SM. Dried whole-plant *Artemisia annua* slows evolution of malaria drug resistance and overcomes resistance to artemisinin. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2015;112(3):821–6.
72. Rasoanaivo P, Wright CW, Willcox ML, Gilbert B. Whole plant extracts versus single compounds for the treatment of malaria: synergy and positive interactions. *Malar J*. 2011;10 Suppl 1(Suppl 1):S4.
73. Jones AW. Early drug discovery and the rise of pharmaceutical chemistry. *Drug Test Anal*. 2011;3(6):337–44.
74. Kumar A, P N, Kumar M, Jose A, Tomer V, Oz E, et al. Major Phytochemicals: Recent Advances in Health Benefits and Extraction Method. *Molecules*. 2023;28(2).
75. Liu YX, Wu W, Liang YJ, Jie ZL, Wang H, Wang W, et al. New uses for old drugs: the tale of artemisinin derivatives in the elimination of schistosomiasis japonica in China. *Molecules*. 2014;19(9):15058–74.
76. O'Neill PM, Barton VE, Ward SA. The molecular mechanism of action of artemisinin--the debate continues. *Molecules*. 2010;15(3):1705–21.
77. Weathers PJ, Arsenault PR, Covello PS, McMickle A, Teoh KH, Reed DW. Artemisinin production in *Artemisia annua*: studies in planta and results of a novel delivery method for treating malaria and other neglected diseases. *Phytochem Rev*. 2011;10(2):173–83.
78. Elfawal MA, Towler MJ, Reich NG, Golenbock D, Weathers PJ, Rich SM. Dried whole plant *Artemisia annua* as an

- antimalarial therapy. *PLoS One*. 2012;7(12):e52746.
79. Weathers PJ, Elfawal MA, Towler MJ, Acquaaah-Mensah GK, Rich SM. Pharmacokinetics of artemisinin delivered by oral consumption of *Artemisia annua* dried leaves in healthy vs. *Plasmodium chabaudi*-infected mice. *J Ethnopharmacol*. 2014;153(3):732–6.
80. Ikeda H, Ishikawa J, Hanamoto A, Shinose M, Kikuchi H, Shiba T, et al. Complete genome sequence and comparative analysis of the industrial microorganism *Streptomyces avermitilis*. *Nat Biotechnol*. 2003;21(5):526–31.
81. Kimura Y, Nakajima H, Hamasaki T. Structure of Rosellichalasin, a New Metabolite Produced by *Rosellinia necatrix*. *Agricultural and Biological Chemistry*. 1989;53(6):1699–701.
82. Chavarro-Carrero EA, Snelders NC, Torres DE, Kraege A, Lopez-Moral A, Petti GC, et al. The soil-borne white root rot pathogen *Rosellinia necatrix* expresses antimicrobial proteins during host colonization. *PLoS Pathog*. 2024;20(1):e1011866.
83. Valli M, Souza JM, Chelucci RC, Biasetto CR, Araujo AR, Bolzani VDS, et al. Identification of natural cytochalasins as leads for neglected tropical diseases drug discovery. *PLoS One*. 2022;17(10):e0275002.
84. Hui F, Scheib U, Hu Y, Sommer RJ, Aroian RV, Ghosh P. Structure and glycolipid binding properties of the nematocidal protein Cry5B. *Biochemistry*. 2012;51(49):9911–21.
85. Kotze AC, O'Grady J, Gough JM, Pearson R, Bagnall NH, Kemp DH, et al. Toxicity of *Bacillus thuringiensis* to parasitic and free-living life-stages of nematode parasites of livestock. *International Journal for Parasitology*. 2005;35(9):1013–22.
86. Wei JZ, Hale K, Carta L, Platzer E, Wong C, Fang SC, et al. *Bacillus thuringiensis* crystal proteins that target nematodes. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2003;100(5):2760–5.
87. Urban JF, Nielsen MK, Gazzola D, Xie Y, Beshah E, Hu Y, et al. An inactivated bacterium (paraprobiotic) expressing *Bacillus thuringiensis* Cry5B as a therapeutic for *Ascaris* and *Parascaris* spp. infections in large animals. *One Health*. 2021;12:100241.
88. Chicca J, Cazeault NR, Rus F, Abraham A, Garceau C, Li H, et al. Efficient and Scalable Process to Produce Novel and Highly Bioactive Purified Cytosolic Crystals from *Bacillus thuringiensis*. *Microbiology Spectrum*. 2022;10(4):e02356–22.
89. Liu X, Ruan L, Peng D, Li L, Sun M, Yu Z. Thuringiensin: a thermostable secondary metabolite from *Bacillus thuringiensis* with insecticidal activity against a wide range of insects. *Toxins (Basel)*. 2014;6(8):2229–38.
90. Shi J, Sun M. *Bacillus thuringiensis*: a gift for nematode management. *Trends Parasitol*. 2025;41(3):235–46.
91. Malovichko YV, Nizhnikov AA, Antonets KS. Repertoire of the *Bacillus thuringiensis* Virulence Factors Unrelated to Major Classes of Protein Toxins and Its Role in Specificity of Host-Pathogen Interactions. *Toxins (Basel)*. 2019;11(6).
92. Emmert EA, Klimowicz AK, Thomas MG, Handelsman J. Genetics of zwittermicin a production by *Bacillus cereus*. *Appl Environ Microbiol*. 2004;70(1):104–13.
93. Broderick NA, Goodman RM, Raffa KF, Handelsman J. Synergy Between Zwittermicin A and *Bacillus thuringiensis* subsp. *kurstaki* Against Gypsy Moth (*Lepidoptera*: *Lymantriidae*). *Environmental Entomology*. 2000;29(1):101–7.
94. Li X, Wang X, Snyder M. Systematic investigation of protein-small molecule interactions. *IUBMB Life*. 2013;65(1):2–8.
95. Lim L, McFadden GI. The evolution, metabolism and functions of the apicoplast. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci*. 2010;365(1541):749–63.
96. Lydon J, John RT, Peter KC. Allelopathic Activity of Annual Wormwood (*Artemisia annua*) and the Role of Artemisinin. *Weed Science*. 1997;45(6):807–11.
97. Duke SO. Herbicide and Pharmaceutical Relationships. *Weed Science*. 2010;58(3):334–9.
98. Firn RD, Jones CG. The evolution of secondary metabolism - a unifying model. *Mol Microbiol*. 2000;37(5):989–94.

99. Salmon M, Laurendon C, Vardakou M, Cheema J, Defernez M, Green S, et al. Emergence of terpene cyclization in *Artemisia annua*. *Nat Commun*. 2015;6:6143.
100. Wagner H, Ulrich-Merzenich G. Synergy research: approaching a new generation of phytopharmaceuticals. *Phytomedicine*. 2009;16(2-3):97–110.
101. Ma L, Zhang X, Xu X, Ke Y, Dai J, Cheng H, et al. Compatibility principle in the Tanyu Tongzhi Formula revealed by a cell-based analysis. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 2019;231:507–15.
102. Sham TT, Chan CO, Wang YH, Yang JM, Mok DK, Chan SW. A review on the traditional Chinese medicinal herbs and formulae with hypolipidemic effect. *Biomed Res Int*. 2014;2014:925302.
103. Zhang YUN, Li Q, Chu X, Zhu J, Lin Y, Liu Y. Traditional Chinese medicine prescription recommendation method based on compatibility principle of monarch, minister, assistant and guide. 2023.
104. Sze SCW, Ip CW, Ng TB, Zhang KY, Zhang Z-J, Cheung HP, et al. Compatibility of multiple herbal components in Erxian Decoction, a Chinese medicinal formula, for treating osteoporosis. *European Journal of Integrative Medicine*. 2012;4(2):e187–e96.
105. Gilleard JS. *Haemonchus contortus* as a paradigm and model to study anthelmintic drug resistance. *Parasitology*. 2013;140(12):1506–22.
106. Fissiha W, Kinde MZ. Anthelmintic Resistance and Its Mechanism: A Review. *Infect Drug Resist*. 2021;14:5403–10.
107. Kotze AC, Prichard RK. Anthelmintic Resistance in *Haemonchus contortus*: History, Mechanisms and Diagnosis. *Adv Parasitol*. 2016;93:397–428.
108. Jimenez Castro PD, Howell SB, Schaefer JJ, Avramenko RW, Gilleard JS, Kaplan RM. Multiple drug resistance in the canine hookworm *Ancylostoma caninum*: an emerging threat? *Parasit Vectors*. 2019;12(1):576.
109. Venkatesan A, Jimenez Castro PD, Morosetti A, Horvath H, Chen R, Redman E, et al. Molecular evidence of widespread benzimidazole drug resistance in *Ancylostoma caninum* from domestic dogs throughout the USA and discovery of a novel beta-tubulin benzimidazole resistance mutation. *PLoS Pathog*. 2023;19(3):e1011146.
110. Ouji M, Augereau JM, Paloque L, Benoit-Vical F. Plasmodium falciparum resistance to artemisinin-based combination therapies: A sword of Damocles in the path toward malaria elimination. *Parasite*. 2018;25:24.
111. Dogovski C, Xie SC, Burgio G, Bridgford J, Mok S, McCaw JM, et al. Targeting the cell stress response of Plasmodium falciparum to overcome artemisinin resistance. *PLoS Biol*. 2015;13(4):e1002132.
112. Tilley L, Straimer J, Gnadig NF, Ralph SA, Fidock DA. Artemisinin Action and Resistance in Plasmodium falciparum. *Trends Parasitol*. 2016;32(9):682–96.
113. Tegos G, Stermitz FR, Lomovskaya O, Lewis K. Multidrug pump inhibitors uncover remarkable activity of plant antimicrobials. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother*. 2002;46(10):3133–41.
114. Dos Santos Barbosa CR, Scherf JR, de Freitas TS, de Menezes IRA, Pereira RLS, Dos Santos JFS, et al. Effect of Carvacrol and Thymol on NorA efflux pump inhibition in multidrug-resistant (MDR) *Staphylococcus aureus* strains. *J Bioenerg Biomembr*. 2021;53(4):489–98.
115. Dias K, Miranda GM, Bessa JR, Araujo ACJ, Freitas PR, Almeida RS, et al. Terpenes as bacterial efflux pump inhibitors: A systematic review. *Front Pharmacol*. 2022;13:953982.
116. Elfawal MA, Savinov SN, Aroian RV. Drug Screening for Discovery of Broad-spectrum Agents for Soil-transmitted Nematodes. *Sci Rep*. 2019;9(1):12347.
117. Xian C, Zhang J, Zhao S, Li XG. Gut-on-a-chip for disease models. *J Tissue Eng*. 2023;14:20417314221149882.
118. Baddal B, Marrazzo P. Refining Host-Pathogen Interactions: Organ-on-Chip Side of the Coin. *Pathogens*. 2021;10(2).

119. Duque-Correa MA, Maizels RM, Grencis RK, Berriman M. Organoids - New Models for Host-Helminth Interactions. *Trends Parasitol.* 2020;36(2):170–81.